

Tracer study of the graduates of Bachelor of Science in Information Technology of the School of Business and Computer Studies for 2015-2016

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Abstract

This tracer study aimed to identify the alumni members of Bachelor of Science in Information Technology, who are now considered professionals and practitioners in their field of expertise. A survey questionnaire was used as the primary tool in collecting data, intended to obtain information on the views of the respondents concerning their academic ratings while still in St. Dominic College of Asia, their present employment status, the length of time they spent in landing their first job, their ways of acquiring a job, the nature of the business they are employed in, their present position and difficulties encountered while looking for a job. Findings showed that majority of the respondents were about 20 to 25 years old, female and had achieved an average academic rating while still in college. The respondent graduates took at least a month to land a job, while others had more than three but less than six months to land a job; taking on jobs that they either saw through the internet, from referrals from friends or associates, or from the classified ads in the newspapers. Most of them were employed in the service industry, or in an educational institution; and there were those who were occupying either rank-and-file or managerial level positions. The respondents also expressed their difficulties which they encountered in seeking employment. Most of them took a satisfactory job related to their field and expressed that they had a hard time competing with other graduates from other colleges or universities, especially those who came from exclusive schools. Both industries and higher education sectors require mutual and thorough capacity growth, particularly in the areas of information technology facilities, which connect theories to computer technology and practical skilling.

Keywords: *Tracer study; Graduates; Alumni members; Bachelor of Science in Information Technology.*

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Introduction

A nation's national advancement relies upon the nature of training that skills and knowledge acquired in the schools, universities, and colleges that they are enlisted in with the assistance and aptitude of value educators and teachers whose duty it is to bestow to the understudies the information and experience that they themselves have additionally picked up in their numerous times of their instructing calling. Each instructive organization ought to oversee monitoring its graduates, as it fills in as a qualifying measure to decide if what the understudies have realized through their times of remain in an establishment have been put to great utilize and have profited them too, and it will likewise decide the foundation's prosperity and its dedication in giving instructive greatness.

A country that fails to provide its population with quality education would ultimately fail in achieving sustainable growth and experience the inevitable consequences of poor productivity, poverty, and mass illiteracy. This will probably be more evident as we now enter the doors of the ASEAN integration, where every aspect will become borderless, especially in business and education. The importance of quality education has long been acknowledged by governments, legislators, and policymakers, and national resources are allocated specifically for higher education to support national growth.

A tracer study of the mapping out of former students of an institution is necessary, for it signifies the evolution and growth of knowledge that the institution has been able to establish through its linkages with higher educational institutions and the companies that their students may be able to work for in the future (Monzon et al., 2022; Yaun & Paronda, 2015). It is believed that the development of a future workforce that will be suitable for various reasons is accomplished through higher education, which also serves as a tool (Owusu, 2021). Various industries have a high and continuous demand for manpower, as proven by the fact that industries look for skills, creativity and innovativeness in prospective applicants, and that is the reason why students have their on-the-job training not only in offices but also in industries as well. This is the reason why educational institutions must continuously maintain linkages with the industrial community to enhance scientific, technological, and socio-economic development.

Therefore, it is imperative that prospective graduates who will soon be employees themselves be trained and re-trained if they are to be recruited for the manpower needs of these various industries, especially in the technical and non-technical fields. The economic recessions being experienced by many countries throughout the world and the liberalization policy would eventually affect the standard of education not only in the Philippines but elsewhere. There is also the aspect wherein higher education may not seem to be aware of the manpower and technological needs of industries in terms of technical know-hows.

Education has not only quantifiable benefits but also externalities such as adaptability to change, family planning, and other values. After all, the brain drain is no longer seen in a negative light due to globalization, and perhaps we should think not only of the local labor market but the global labor market as well. Depending on the degree, different professional knowledge was utilized differently.

However, it is necessary for the school to determine the whereabouts of its graduates and the applicability of its course offerings in consonance with the least requirements of the industry. It was observed from the study that the most important abilities and attitudes required of the graduates were the following: sense of responsibility, self-confidence, reliability, willingness to perform, commitment, ability to solve problems, initiative, willingness to learn, ability to coordinate, ability to work under pressure, and leadership qualities.

The tracing and mapping of student graduates in this study was done to find out how much higher education has contributed to the professional careers of SDCA graduates, how the effectiveness of higher education in meeting job needs could be assessed, and how our graduates would be able to find employment, and how their creative and innovative skills could be enhanced (Deblois, 2021). In terms of how the results of this study would be evaluated, it would serve the purpose of effectively assessing the contribution of higher education and how effective it was on the individual, meaning, to what extent this would be beneficial to the student graduate in terms of his finding employment and developing further his skills and knowledge.

There were very few, if any, studies done on tracing and mapping out of student graduates in terms of how higher education contributed to organizational development, how new knowledge and expertise would be acceptable within the organization and how it would be used in effectively changing routines, the structure, and the functions within the organization, and how new ways of doing things that have not been done before would be helpful in transforming the organization (Sharma, 2014). This was made more apparent when higher education was associated with the nation-building task, as the case was with higher education offered to graduates from developing countries. The purpose of this was to impart new knowledge, enhance capacity, and form a new identity to empower graduates to contribute to organization building.

This survey was a research effort designed to offer useful data for assessing the training and education outcomes of a particular higher education institution. The institution may utilize this information to advance its development in the quality assurance competition. This method was also used by the higher education institution to gather data that would help identify any potential weaknesses in each program and provide a foundation for future planning initiatives. It was necessary to gather data on the graduates' professional achievement as well as the applicability of their knowledge and abilities (relationship between knowledge and job requirements, field of work, and professional position). Graduates were additionally requested to evaluate the study resources and conditions they had previously encountered (Schomburg, 2003).

The graduate and employer surveys were important for measuring the output and outcomes of higher education as well as the effect and desirable forms of teaching and study. Measuring the output alone and ignoring such information as output and input for improvements only leads to fruitless research; thus, it was also the intention of this research to evaluate the performance of the college as to the knowledge production, which was the process involved in teaching and knowledge transfer, referring to the process by which the respondent can use to apply knowledge acquired.

This survey was also intended to contribute innovation and, expectedly, to improve the course and to address the issues concerning curriculum evaluation, identity formation, recognition, and reputation, as well as the enhancement of status and social position. It is the intention of this study to give recommendations to improve the study conditions and the academic program offerings. and likewise, to answer the needs of industry. From this study, the school will be able to determine the appropriate measures to be taken to improve the quality of education among students so that the graduates can be in a competitive position.

Important prerequisites for the teaching and learning processes were the study circumstances, resources, and obligations of the universities. These included the university's physical layout, the lab and library equipment, the number of students per faculty member, and the instructors' standing in the scientific community. University procedures include, for instance, the educational activities that take place in the lectures, guidance given to students, the involvement of students in research, and, in a limited sense, the attainment of the intended output and, in a more general sense, the impact or results. For instance, the discrepancy between the graduate's actual qualifications and the overestimated symbolic nature of the diploma, which involves not only separating the methods of measuring abilities but also highlighting the momentum gained by statements regarding qualifications in diplomas; and, secondly, the discrepancy between the study's actual results and subsequent activities and performances in both professional and other areas of life (Schomburg, 2003).

The transition phase was defined as the amount of time spent looking for a job between graduation and the first regular job, the number of applications that were accepted or rejected, the length of time spent looking for a job, a longer term of unemployment, and the status and employment characteristics of the job. Universities and schools were primarily interested in interpreting the value of such transition-related achievement; as a result, assessments of the professional output gained during studies could be obtained at the start of employment. According to this perspective, the first job's attributes could be interpreted as an indicator for career achievement, the true worth of which can only be verified by examining the relationship or correlation between the initial job's success and subsequent professional success. These include remarks about the overall qualities of the profession, its standing and reputation, and professional satisfaction, all of which were impacted by perceptions of what was ideal for the field. For example, the opportunity to apply learned skills, the autonomy of decision-making at work, the potential for additional professional development, positive collaboration with colleagues, and workplace safety (Schomburg, 2003).

Additionally, graduates were asked which academic subjects they thought were particularly helpful and which of the credentials they had earned for their studies were used in their jobs. All things considered, it is important to emphasize that the graduates were able to evaluate how the credentials they had earned during their academic careers were applied and how well the knowledge they had gained aligned with their professional roles (Schomburg, 2003). Locating the graduates and getting feedback from them were vital ingredients of tracer studies, especially when graduates return to their work. This was not an easy task since the college does not possess an up-to-date address list of the graduates who was also a by-product of the study.

It is with this in mind that the researchers saw the importance of making this study, for it will be truly meaningful to St. Dominic College of Asia if the mapping out of its students could be done so that it would know how useful the theories and actual practices in the students' education would help them in the future performance of their job, how the future of the respondents would be affected if ever the jobs that they would get into would only be sideline jobs, what kind of income would they earn and would they have any benefits at all, what the respondents' thinking would be in terms of their occupational characteristics, what they would be able to expect in their future careers, what actualizations they would have in the world of work, and how the respondents would be able to tackle the working conditions that they might find themselves in, what kind of experiences they would have, and what kind of expectations their employers would have of them.

Statement of the Problem

This study determined whether the respondents' specific work assignments are related to their field of study, how they obtained their first job, and whether the theoretical and practical aspects of their education were useful to their job performance. It aims to find out how the respondents cope with their working conditions, experiences, and employers' expectations, as well as how they perceive and feel about their professional features, career expectations, actualization, and changes.

Through this study, the present standing of Bachelor of Science in Information alumni members as professionals and practitioners in their field of expertise will be known and identified. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following:

1. What is the profile of the respondents as to:
 - a) Age
 - b) Gender
 - c) Civil status
 - d) Year graduated
2. What are the challenges that have affected their quest for employment in terms of:
 - a) Company requirements in the screening of applicants
 - b) Waiting time for the reply for work

- c) Ways in acquiring a job / work
 - d) Difficulties encountered while job hunting
3. What is the professional status of the respondents in terms of:
 - a) Current career status
 - b) Salary / Compensation
 - c) Current work
 - d) Length of stay in their work
4. What advantages did the respondents acquire from St. Dominic College of Asia and the School of Business and Computer Studies that helped them attain their present professional status?
5. What are the factors that need improvement as perceived by the respondents about the College where they came from?

This study was limited to graduates of Bachelor of Science in Information Technology for the years 2015-2016.

Methodology

Research Design

This study uses the descriptive type of research to gather data on the tracer study of graduates of the Information Technology department. The respondents of this tracer study were the graduates chosen purposefully from the school year 2015-2016. The total population of this study consisted of 24 graduates. The researchers sent 24 questionnaires to all the graduates and retrieved all answered questionnaires. The survey took three weeks, and those who returned their answered questionnaires were qualified as respondents to this study, and those who did not participate significantly affected the results of this study.

Research Instruments and Techniques Used

1. Questionnaire

The questionnaire, which was created to gather data on respondents' opinions, served as the main instrument for this study concerning the study conditions and provisions, employment and career/occupation relevance, qualifications acquired, organizational development relevance, their personal orientation, attitudes towards work, and innovativeness. The same instrument was also used to gather information on the respondents' profile and their motives or reasons for finishing their studies.

The questionnaire was divided into several parts. The first part was about their profile as to age, gender, year graduated, and their present employment status. The second part of the questionnaire asked how long the respondents took to land their first job after graduating from college. the way of acquiring their job or work, the nature of the business, their present position in the company, and the difficulties they had in finding a job.

The draft questionnaires were presented to the dean, who was requested to check the contents and the validity of each item contained therein. Several suggestions, revisions, and corrections were made upon their recommendation. The questionnaires were also presented to some research educators of the college to measure its understandability and for further validation of its content.

Pre-testing and post-testing of the contents were made, and any suggestions to improve the structure of the questions as well as the structure of the indicators were incorporated in the final copy of the questionnaires. The researchers also used SPSS software to further validate the contents of the questionnaires, of which the statistical output coefficient was 0.9074, proving further that the questions were substantially related to each other.

2. Unstructured Interview

The researchers conducted unstructured interviews with some of the respondents to bring forth additional information that could enhance the responses on the questionnaires. The respondents were encouraged to provide relevant details related to the contents of the questionnaire.

3. Internet and Information Technology

The researchers used the internet and information technology to gather data that was relevant to the study. Several useful statistics, figures, and related studies were publicly posted on the internet. The researchers chose which of those figures were relevant for inclusion in their study, including several related literatures available on the internet.

4. Documentary Analysis

The researchers used documentary analysis for data that can be gathered from published materials, records, and data pertinent to the research. Data numbers of graduates, names, and their addresses were made available using documentary analysis.

Data Gathering

One aspect in which the researchers were attentive in collecting data was about the validity and reliability. To avoid biases, data were collected through structured questionnaires wherein the respondents were anonymous, and they could fill it out in private. Moreover, some alumni members may send the questionnaires through postal mail at a later stage. In addition, several informal conversations were held with alumni to obtain reliable and valid data.

At the same time, it may be said that closeness makes it possible to obtain reliable and valid data. Closeness was associated with trust between the Dean and respondents. This was essential, particularly in tracer studies where closeness allows access and ensures appropriate respondents and information. Since respondents in tracer studies involved a particular group, closeness allows for better and quicker access. Moreover, given the time and resource constraints, an “outsider” or “neutral” researcher would have found it difficult to locate the alumni and get access to them to obtain reliable and valid data.

Visiting the graduates in their respective workplaces or at home may have several positive consequences. First, the students may be proud that their faculty member sent a researcher to visit them. They may feel that they were given recognition and were still part of the college even after their graduation. It enhanced their belongingness to the college and to the program. The visit was clearly a moral booster for the alumni. Second, the visit will enhance the social position vis-à-vis their colleagues. The colleagues can witness that their college still maintains contact with the alumni. Never has it happened that a college representative paid a visit to their former students and had discussions with them as well as with their colleagues. The visit by the researchers has, therefore, symbolic value for students, which was an important ingredient in the alumni’s social life and professional career.

The profile of the respondents was measured by the age, gender, the field of study for which they were awarded their bachelor’s degree, the school year the respondents graduated, and the highest degree obtained from the last year that they completed their highest education. The extent of the importance and the reasons for choosing college to pursue higher education were also considered to determine the significance of the perceptions of the three groups of respondents. These will be measured by the means of the following: educators’ accessibility to work, home, and neighborhood, to parents and relatives; grants, scholarships, and other discounts being given by the college; favorable accommodation by the student and staff of the graduate school; attractiveness of the school in terms of facilities and instruction; reputation of the school in the community and in the academy; and in the industry, practice-oriented curriculum applicable to one’s profession; and a reputable line-up of faculty members for the graduate student.

The study provisions and conditions experienced during their study and the usefulness of their graduate studies were also measured with the current activities, employment, and work as correlated with their qualification, together with some suggestions on the improvement of the graduate school. The research paradigm showed the personal rating done by the respondents themselves and measured accordingly as to excellent, very good, good, and average. This research also measured the employment status of the respondents, the manner of acquiring a job, the nature of the business, the difficulties encountered by the respondents in getting a job, and the recommendations that were also considered in the study.

Percentage (P). This was used by the researchers to determine the ratio of the frequency of responses, (f), of the respondents to the total number, (N), of the respondents. This was expressed in percent as $P = (f/N) \times 100\%$.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 represents the profile of the respondent as to age, gender, academic ratings, and present employment status.

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents (n=24)

Profile		f	%	Rank
Age	Below 20 years old	3	12.5	1
	20-25 years old	21	87.5	2
Gender	Male	5	20.8	2
	Female	19	79.2	1
Academic Rating	Excellent	3	12.5	3
	Very Good	4	16.7	2
	Good	16	66.7	1
	Average	1	4.2	4
Present Employment Status	Employed	15	62.5	1
	Not Employed	2	8.3	3
	Unreachable	7	29.2	2

Findings showed that most of the respondents were about 20–25 years old, representing 87.5% of the total respondents. Most of these respondents were females and have achieved “good” academic ratings while still in college compared with the rest of the respondents, representing males with about 20.8% of the respondents. Findings also showed that these graduate respondents were employed locally.

Table 2. Ways of Finding a Job (n=24)

Particulars	f	%	Rank
From the internet	15	62.5	1
From friends	5	20.8	2
From newspaper advertisement	4	16.7	3

Findings also showed that most of the respondents, about 16.8%, got their jobs from newspaper advertisements and about 62.4% from the internet. This implies that most of the graduates had to seek employment from advertisements coming from the industry sector on the internet (Loquias, 2015). This matter needs the attention of the guidance and placement office of the college, and it must provide a placement section where linkage with industries must be made.

Table 3. Waiting for the Reply for Work (n=24)

Particulars	f	%	Rank
Less than 1 month	14	58.3	1
1-2 months	10	41.7	2

58.3% of the respondents took their first job within one month, and 41.7% landed their first job between two months. The respondent graduates took at least one month to land a job, while others already had their jobs, and others took more than two months but less than a year to land a job.

Table 4. Difficulties Encountered in Finding a Job (n=24)

Particulars	f	%	Rank
Taking a satisfactory job not related to one's field	7	29.2	1
Pay is low	5	20.8	2
Does not like the jobs available	4	16.7	3
Could not get a satisfactory job	2	8.3	5.5
Inadequate training	2	8.3	5.5
Could not compete with other graduates	2	8.3	5.5
No job available in the market	2	8.3	5.5

Table 4 showed the difficulties encountered by the graduates in finding a job; hence, taking satisfactorily a job not related to his or her field had 29.2% ranked as first: could not get a satisfactory job with 8.3%; pay is low had 20.8%; does not like the jobs available had 16.7%; inadequate training had 8.3%; no job available in the market with 8.3%; and lastly, could not compete with other graduates with 8.3%. This result implied some deficiencies in the instructions and in the programs offered. It is suggested that a revisit of the program offerings is necessary, and hence, this study was deemed essential and timely, considering the nature of the business and the present positions occupied by the graduates. The results showed that most of the graduates, about 27%, were in education.

This result implied that the information technology students were somewhat geared towards education. It was very unlikely that a graduate of information technology should devote his career to education unless the respondent felt that educating the youth was his calling. However, an information technology graduate is always expected to be in the industry or somewhat connected within the industry (McKenzie et al., 2018; Nyasulu et al., 2019). After considering the many difficulties that the respondents had in landing a job after their graduation, the respondents suggested to update curriculum syllabi and add more subjects in the IT course.

Nature of Graduates that Are Employed In

Most of the graduates were in the service industry, either in food or in other service firms; thus, evidence that most of the graduates have a difficult time seeking an appropriate job or a job that will fit their qualifications. Furthermore, the table showed that 62%, or most of the graduates, were in rank-and-file positions, and about 20% were in managerial positions. These results implied that the curriculum of the school needs enhancement to answer the needs of the industry; however, some respondents found their work in financial institutions, 13% in commercial establishments, and 18% in banking, and there was a need to revisit the program so that the graduates would have their chance to be in an industry, as evidenced by the responses shown.

Conclusions

In general, it is certain that graduates use their knowledge and intellectual abilities effectively enough in industries. Because most workplaces now have the much-discussed modern facilities and technologies, students typically face challenges from the shifting demands of the industries and technological advancements, to which they may not have been adequately exposed in the school setting during their time there (JJ/WGBSP, 2007).

Both industries and higher education profiles require mutual and thorough capacity growth, particularly in the areas of information technology infrastructures, which connect theories to computer technology and practical skilling. The following specific recommendations were proposed to accomplish the intended comprehensive capacity growth:

- Better funding for the higher education institution is required to increase their total capability for the provision of essential equipment and study facilities that would improve their study conditions.
- The school's administration should do more in terms of improving the study conditions of their students.
- Higher education should adopt a more board-based and interdisciplinary approach to curriculum development, evaluation, and assessment.
- Practice-oriented study or the acquisition of multiple and practical abilities (like computer language skills) should be given more than enough attention. To keep up with technical and sociocultural advancements, the study curriculum must be updated at least every two years.

Since these graduates have encountered some difficulties, personal or otherwise, in looking for a suitable job, the following internal recommendations were formulated:

1. The Office of Student Life or the guidance office should design a program that will provide employment and/or placement to graduates. By benchmarking other colleges and universities, it was found that each guidance office provided a placement office by holding job fairs at least twice in an academic year, and if necessary, they should recommend student graduates to companies.
2. A well-designed and strong faculty development program should be given to faculty members regularly and should be linked to industry requirements, and closer ties should be established with various industries whenever necessary.
3. Stronger linkages with industries, local and international, should be established to permit self-evaluation of courses and subject offerings.

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